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**Polysaccharide from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*
Linn. Seeds-isolation, Purification and
Preliminary Analysis of Polysaccharide**

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NYCTANTHES *arbor-tristis* Linn. (Fam. : Oleaceae ; Hindi : *Harsingar*, *Parajita*) is a large shrub, 15-25 feet high and is widely cultivated as a garden plant throughout India. The seeds are known for their use in Ayurvedic system of medicine for throat, leprosy, eye diseases, skin infections, intestinal worm infection etc. The systematic chemical investigation of the seed polysaccharide has not been reported so far. The present communication reports the isolation of a polysaccharide in the pure form, and the nature of the constituent sugars.

Experimental

Isolation : The seeds (200 g) were washed with water to remove completely the outer covering. Subsequently the seeds were crushed in a hand grinder into a greyish white powder. The powder (100 g) was soaked in water (900 ml) overnight and

stirred for 48 h. The resulting viscous solution was squeezed through muslin cloth and centrifuged at 25000 r.p.m. in Sharple's super centrifuge to remove finely suspended matter. The centrifugate was treated with ethanol (2 dm³) to precipitate the polysaccharide in the form of light brown coarse powder. It was filtered through sintered funnel (G-3) under suction and the residual polysaccharide dried *in vacuo* at 60° after washing with acetone and ether. The white amorphous powder of the polysaccharide (8.2 g) had sulphated ash 1.982%, as determined by sulphated ash method¹; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 32^\circ$ (H₂O).

Purification : The above polysaccharide (2 g) was dissolved in water (200 ml) with constant mechanical stirring for 12 h and the solution treated with ethanol in stages. First the concentration of ethanol was made upto 20% in the solution. It precipitated out some impurities which was allowed to settle overnight and then centrifuged. The centrifugate was further treated with ethanol to have its concentration to 30% in the solution to precipitate higher molecular weight polysaccharide and removed by centrifugation. Ethanol concentration in the supernatant liquor was increased to 40% and then to 60%, when rest of the polysaccharides precipitated out. The polysaccharide obtained by 40% and 60% ethanol concentration were triturated with absolute ethanol, acetone and ether and dried over calcium chloride *in vacuo* at 60° (1.5240 g), sulphated ash 0.632%; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 28.4^\circ$ (H₂O) for 40%, and $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 29.2^\circ$ (H₂O) for 60%, respectively. This indicated that the two polysaccharides were probably identical and this was corroborated by their identical infrared spectra.

The purified polysaccharide was in the form of white amorphous powder; it did not reduce Fehling's solution. Nitrogen, sulphur, halogens, acetyl group², uronic acid³, methoxyl group⁴, pentosans⁵, pentoses⁶ and furfural⁶ were absent in it and it formed a highly viscous solution in water.

Nature of sugars : The purified polysaccharide (2 g) was kept with sulphuric acid⁸ (72%, 8 ml) overnight at room temperature. The slurry was cooled in a freezing mixture and diluted with water (112 ml) to make up a normal solution with respect to sulphuric acid. The solution was heated for 12 h at 100° in boiling water-bath, when the hydrolysis which was followed iodometrically⁷, was found to be completed.

The hydrolysate was neutralised with barium carbonate and filtered. The resulting solution, was passed through Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺) and Amberlite IR-45 (OH⁻) ion-exchange resins and concentrated to a thin syrup. P.c. by descending method^{9,10} using *n*-butanol-ethanol-water mixture (4:1:5, upper phase)¹⁰ and *p*-anisidine phosphate¹¹ as a spray reagent, revealed the presence of glucose and mannose.

Resolution of sugars by column chromatography : A column of Whatman standard chromatographic

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cellulose powder was prepared in a glass tube (55×2 cm) fitted with glass stopper. Medium size slurry of nearly 25 g of cellulose powder was prepared by blending in Sumit blender with the solvent *n*-butanol half saturated with water^{1,2} for 2 min. The column was washed with the eluting solvent, *n*-butanol half saturated with water till the washing became colourless. The homogeneity of the column was tested with methyl red dye. The column was again washed with the same solvent to remove the dye.

The sugar mixture in the form of a thin syrup (2 ml) was introduced in the column and allowed to drain and then eluted. The effluent was collected in 10 ml portions. The fractions were examined by paper chromatography and found to contain the sugars as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESOLUTION OF SUGAR MIXTURE ON CELLULOSE COLUMN

Fraction no.	Sugar present
1—40	No sugar
41—56	D-mannose only
57—76	Mixture of D-mannose and D-glucose
76—96	D-glucose only
96	No sugar

Characterisation of sugars: Appropriate fractions of the eluate containing single pure sugar were combined together and concentrated. D-Glucose and D-mannose were identified, D-glucose, m.p. and m.m.p. 144-146°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 52.9^\circ$ (c, 0.5 H₂O); D-mannose, m.p. and m.m.p. 130-131°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 12.2^\circ$ (c, 0.5 H₂O).

The aqueous solution of D-mannose (25 ml) was taken in a flask and glacial acetic acid (10 drops) and phenylhydrazine (5 drops) were added and shaken. The flask (cork loosely fitted) was kept in the boiling water-bath for 10 min and shaken periodically. A yellow precipitate of D-mannose phenylhydrazone^{1,3} was obtained. It was recrystallised from ethanol and dried, m.p. and m.m.p. 194-196°.

Aqueous solution of D-glucose (20 ml) was taken in a flask and glacial acetic acid (8 drops) and phenylhydrazine (4 drops) were added and shaken thoroughly and heated in boiling water-bath for 10 min, shaking the flask at short intervals. A bulky yellow precipitate of D-glucose osazone^{1,4} was obtained, m.p. and m.m.p. 202-204°.

Quantitative estimation of sugars: For quantitative estimation of sugars^{1,5}, the purified polysaccharide (260 mg) was heated at 100° with sulphuric acid (1N, 10 ml) in a sealed tube for 26 h over boiling water-bath and processed as usual. The hydrolysate was separated on Whatman No. 3 filter paper using *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (4 : 1 : 5, upper phase)^{1,6} as solvent. The corresponding strips were cut out with the help of guide spots and sugars were eluted with water according to Dent's method^{1,6}.

The eluted sugars were estimated by periodate oxidation method^{1,6}. Necessary corrections for the blank readings were made. The molar ratio of D-glucose and D-mannose was 1 : 3.

Some information about the nature of linkages in the polysaccharide was obtained from its infrared spectra in KBr. Absorption bands at 814 and 874 cm⁻¹ were observed which indicated α -linkages in D-glucopyranose and β -linkages in D-mannopyranose units^{1,7}.

The pure polysaccharide was taken up for methylation and periodate oxidation studies.

Results and Discussion

The seeds of *N. arbor-tristis* gives a water soluble polysaccharide consisting D-glucose and D-mannose. The molar ratio of these two sugars is 1 : 3, thereby indicating that the polysaccharide is a glucomannan. Since the rotation of the parent polysaccharide is low positive, the anomeric linkage is predominantly of β -type possibly with few α -type. It has also been observed from its spectrum that D-glucopyranose units have α -linkage while D-mannopyranoses have β -linkage.

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